

INDIRECT TRANSLATION IN EVERYDAY AND INSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATION OF UKRAINIAN REFUGEES IN POLAND: A CASE STUDY

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This presentation investigates the pragmatic role of *indirect translation* in everyday and institutional communication among Ukrainian refugees who settled in a medium-sized Polish city Rzeszów, as a result of the war in Ukraine in 2022. Indirect translation is traditionally overlooked in Translation Studies, yet it constitutes a significant linguistic strategy in multilingual and crisis contexts (Gambier, 1994). Building on the conceptual framework provided by the IndirecTrans project, which highlights indirect translation as a norm-governed, culturally mediated practice (Pięta, 2021; IndirecTrans), this study highlights the lived experiences of refugees navigating public services in a host community with limited direct Ukrainian – Polish interpreting resources.

The analysis is based on a structured questionnaire administered to Ukrainian refugees in Rzeszów, focussing on their reliance on intermediary languages (e.g., English and Russian) when communicating with schools, offices, healthcare providers and employment intermediaries. Results allow the formulation of questions regarding the role of indirect translation as a practical communication strategy where direct professional mediation is not available, as well as the ethical and quality-related challenges associated with it, such as accuracy and access to information. This reflection also considers the importance of indirect translation in the context of specialised texts and in communication between communities that are seemingly linguistically close, where problems may arise due to phenomena such as “false friends,” i.e., words that look similar but have divergent meanings, whose clarification may require recourse to pivot languages.

References:

1. Gambier, Y. (1994). La retraduction, retour et détour. *Meta: Journal des traducteurs*, 39(3), 413–417. <https://doi.org/10.7202/002799ar> IndirecTrans. (n.d.). About indirect translation. Retrieved January 21, 2026, from <https://www.indirecttrans.com/about-indirect-translation.html>
2. Pięta, H. (2021). Indirect translation. In Y. Gambier & L. van Doorslaer (Eds.), *Handbook of Translation Studies* (Vol. 5, pp. 113–119). Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/hts.5.ind2>.